

Relativistic Corrections to the Schrodinger Problem Associated with a Kratzer Potential And a Pseudoscalar Coulomb Term

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In (1), an exact solution is found for the Dirac equations for a 1D problem with a scalar potential of $-2D(a/|x| - .5 qaa/(xx))$ and a vector potential of $-b/|x|$. The Dirac equations are first decoupled to obtain two second order DEs and these are solved as hypergeometric equations, after a transformation. An expression for energy is found which depends on rest mass.

The objective of this note is to try to use the method of (2),(3) to find the corresponding nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation and then a relativistic correction to its energy. We show the ground state Schrodinger solution may be obtained by inspection. We also obtain the first order relativistic energy correction. The form of the DE needed to compute this correction, however, is the same as the Schrodinger equation and the full relativistic case for this example, although constant coefficients are different. Thus, one may use the approach for solving the Schrodinger equation for the full problem and obtain a ground state result. An interesting result which emerges is the dependence of the Schrodinger energy on a series of various orders of m . The leading term is a constant (in terms of m) and the second term of order $1/\sqrt{m}$. The next term is of order $m^{-3/2}$. Finding the first relativistic correction yields a term of order $1/m$ which is in between these two values. Thus, the Schrodinger result seems to contain some "relativistic corrections", but not others, as has been pointed out in the literature before.

Relativistic Problem

In (1), the authors obtain two decoupled Dirac equations for the scalar potential: $-2D(a/|x| - .5 qaa/(xx))$ and vector potential: $-b/|x|$. (One may see the terms are related to $1/x$ and its spatial derivative.

We consider the first equation:

$$-d/dx d/dx W + (E+M)(-2D(a/|x| - .5 qaa/(xx)) W + b*b/(x*x) W + d/dx b/|x| W =$$

$$(EE-mm) W \quad ((1))$$

The authors use the variable $y = 2\sqrt{mm-ee} x$ and the transformation: $\exp(-y/2) y^p f(y)$ to cast ((1)) into the form of a hypergeometric equation with a constraint on p . The factor $\exp(-y/2)$ when acted upon by $-d/dx d/dx$ cancels the term $(EE-mm)$. Such a factor is also often used in solving the Klein-Gordon equation. First and second derivatives of y^p will mimic the potential terms. The details of the relativistic solution are given in (1). The transformation leads to a hypergeometric DE (not a Nikiforov-Uvarov equation) which has automatic solutions for the energy levels and wavefunction.

The energy $E_n = e + m$ is given by:

$$(m + E_n) / (m - E_n) = 1 / (D D a a) [n + .5 + \sqrt{.25 + g}]^2 \quad ((2))$$

where $g = D(E_n + m) q a a + b(b + 1)$. Thus, g contains information about both potentials.

One may use ((2)) to obtain the first order term e_0 from $E_n = e_0 + d_e + m$. One may also obtain the first order correction. The first order energy is and one correction is:

$$e_0 = -D/q [1 - 1 / \sqrt{2m D q a a}] \quad ((3))$$

To obtain d_e one uses:

$$(2m + e_0 + d_e) / (e_0 + d_e) = 1 / (D D a a) \{ (n + .5)^2 + .25 + D q a a (2m + e_0 + d_e) + b(b - 1) + 2(n + .5) \sqrt{2D m q a a} [1 + .5(e_0 + d_e) / (2D m) + b(b - 1) / (2D m q a a)] \} \quad ((4))$$

Thus, the $O(1/m)$ d_e terms is:

$$d_e = e_0 (n + .5) a (\sqrt{q}) \{ 1 + b(b - 1) / (q a a) \} \{ 1 / (\sqrt{2D m}) \} \{ 1 / [D D a a - (n + .5)^2 - .25 - b(b - 1)] \}$$

$$\text{Or } 2m d_e = 1 / (2a a q q) \quad ((5))$$

Non-relativistic Correction

The approach of (2)(3) for finding relativistic corrections is to begin with the relativistic equation. Next, all spatial derivatives d/dx are kept the same, but the relativistic wavefunction is $W(x)$ is replaced with $W_0(x) + W_1(x) + \dots$ where $W_0(x)$ is the Schrodinger or Schrodinger-like equation solution. Also, $E = e + m$ where $e = e_0 + d_e + \dots$. Where e_0 is the Schrodinger energy. Finally, for a nonrelativistic solution, it is assumed that $e_0 \ll 2m$. Thus, e enters into correction terms. We try to apply this method to ((1)).

Taking terms with high m coefficients as well as $-d/dx d/dx W_0$ terms which may bring down an "m" term, we obtain:

$$-d/dx d/dx W_0 + m (-2D(a/|x| - .5 q a a / (x x)) W_0(x) = 2m e_0 W_0(x) \quad ((6))$$

We use $E + m \approx 2m$ for our first approximation. One may note the vector potential does not enter into ((6)) which is expected. The Schrodinger equation only uses one potential.

Equation ((6)) may be solved exactly as a hypergeometric equation, but here we wish to find rapidly the ground state solution. We use $W_0 = x^p g(x)$. Then:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_0 = -p(p-1) x^{(p-2)} g - 2g' p x^{p-1} - x^p g''$$

Next:

$-p(p-1) + mD qaa = 0$ to find $p = \sqrt{Daqq2m}$ for large m . It is, however, good to calculate further corrections.

$$p = \frac{1}{2} \pm \sqrt{\frac{1}{4} + mDaqq} = \frac{1}{2} \pm \sqrt{mDaqq} \left\{ 1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{4} mDaaqq \right) + \dots \right\}$$

$$2pg' - 2Da2mg = 0 \text{ or } g = \exp(-Da2m/px). \quad ((6a))$$

Finally: $-g'' - 2meog = 0$ which yields $e_0 = -D/q$ as a first approximation which matches the result from the relativistic calculation. Using the full p in ((6a)), however, will already yield corrections to the Schrodinger equation, in fact, an entire series of them in powers of $(m^{-1/2})^n$. These, however, are not the only corrections as is seen next. Thus, the Schrodinger energy is a strange mix of a first order energy and a portion of the relativistic correction terms.

Given e_0 and $W_0(x)$ for the ground state from above, we now try to establish an equation for e_1 , the first relativistic correction to e_0 . We use:

$$S = (-2D \frac{a}{|x|} - 5 qaa / (xx)) = S_1/x + S_2/(xx) \text{ and } V_p = b/|x|$$

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W_1(x) + m S W_1(x) + e_0 S W_0(x) + V_p^* V_p W_0(x) + \frac{d}{dx} V_p W_0(x) = 2m e_1 W_0(x) + e_1 W_0(x) \quad ((6))$$

This equation is not particularly simply to solve even though e_0 and W_0 are known, nor is it necessary to solve it. One may go back to the original relativistic equation ((1)) and add terms that were dropped in the Schrodinger case. In particular, one obtains the original relativistic result:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + (2m+e)S W + \frac{b(b-1)}{(xx)} W = (e_1+2me) W \quad ((7))$$

One may incorporate $b(b-1)/(xx)$ with $S_2/(xx)$ so one has $S_2 b/(xx)$ and $S_b = S_1/x + (S_2 + b(b-1)/(2m+e_0)) / (xx)$. Then ((7)) becomes:

$$-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W + (2m+e) S_b W = (e_1+2me) W \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is of the same form as the Schrodinger equation; only the constant coefficients differ. We solve the ground state case.

$$\left(\frac{1}{(xx)} \text{ coefficient} \right) -p(p-1) + (2m+e) S_b^2 = 0$$

$p = .5 + \sqrt{.25 - 4Sb^2(2m+e)}$ Later, an m expansion will be made.

$$(1/x \text{ coefficient}) \quad 2g'p(2m+e) S1 g = 0 \quad \text{or } g = \exp[-S1(2m+e)/2p x] \quad ((9))$$

Then:

$$ee + 2me = -S1S1(4mm + ee + 4me) (1/(4 S2b 2m) (1 - e/2m + 1/(4 Sb^2 m) + \dots))$$

Taking high m power terms gives:

$$Ee + 2me = -S1 S1 / (4S2b 2m) [4mm + 4m/(16 S2b)] \quad ((10))$$

The leading m terms gives $e=D/q$ although it is known from the Schrodinger equation that there is a second $1/\sqrt{m}$ order term.

Next, consider $e=e_0+de$. The ee term on the LHS drops out and:

$$2m de = -S1 S1 / (4 S2b) * (1/ (8 S2b)) \quad ((11))$$

For the time being consider $b=0$ or $S2b= S2$. Then: $S1S1/ S2S2 = 4/(qqaa)$

$$\text{So } 2mde = 1/ (2 qq aa) \quad ((12))$$

One may consider the full $S2b$ term. Then one has:

$$2mde = -(1/8) DDaa / (Dqaa + b(b-1)/ (2m+e_0))^2$$

One may next compare with the full relativistic result for the ground state $n=0$ ((5)) which is:

$$2m de = 1/ (2qq aa). \quad \text{Thus } ((12)) \text{ and } ((5)) \text{ agree.}$$

To obtain the correction from the relativistic result, we use:

$$(2m + e_0 + de) / (e_0 (1+de/e_0)) = 2m/e_0 + 1 - 2mde/(e_0e_0) \text{ on the LHS of } ((2)).$$

The RHS is expanded in powers of m .

Conclusion

In this somewhat unusual problem, the DE for the Schrodinger equation is of the same form as the full relativistic one, although constant coefficients change. For example, the vector

potential is dropped in the Schrodinger case, but its form $V_p^*V_p$ and $d/dx V_p$ yield $b(b-1)/(xx)$ which combines with a term of the scalar potential. Solving the Schrodinger equation first, shows that there are a series of m order terms associated with e_0 , one proportional to a constant and the rest proportional to integer powers of $1/\sqrt{m}$. The first relativistic correction to the energy then becomes proportional to $1/m$ which sits between a constant and $1/\sqrt{m}$. Thus, the Schrodinger energy seems to be a hybrid of a constant leading energy term and a partial set of correction terms (integer powers of $1/\sqrt{m}$), while relativistic corrections yield a first correction of $1/m$ in addition to other corrections.

References

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